

1 **Canopy occupation volume as an indicator of canopy photosynthetic capacity**

2 Fusang Liu¹, Qingfeng Song^{1*}, Jinke Zhao¹, Linxiong Mao^{1,3}, Hongyi Bu², Yong Hu²
3 and Xin-Guang Zhu^{1*}

4
5 ¹ National Key Laboratory of Plant Molecular Genetics, CAS Center for Excellence in
6 Molecular Plant Sciences, Shanghai Institute of Plant Physiology and Ecology, Chinese
7 Academy of Sciences, Shanghai 200031, China

8 ² Shanghai Institute of Technical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Shanghai
9 200083, China

10 ³ University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, 100049, China

11
12 * Correspondence: zhuxg@cemps. ac. cn and songqf@cemps.ac.cn

13
14 **ORCID**

15 Fusang Liu: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8867-6712>

16 Qingfeng Song: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4314-6897>

17 Xin-Guang Zhu: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4435-130X>

18
19
20 **Summary**

- 21 • Leaf angle and leaf area index together influence canopy light interception and
22 canopy photosynthesis. However, so far, there is no effective method to identify the
23 optimal combination of these two parameters for canopy photosynthesis.
- 24 • In this study, first a robust high-throughput method for accurate segmentation of
25 maize organs based on 3D point clouds data was developed, then the segmented
26 plant organs were used to generate new 3D point clouds for the canopy of altered
27 architectures. With this, we simulated the synergistic effect of leaf area and leaf
28 angle on canopy photosynthesis.

- 29 • The results show that, compared to the traditional parameters describing the canopy
30 photosynthesis including leaf area index, facet angle and canopy coverage, a new
31 parameter, i.e., the canopy occupation volume (COV), can better explain the
32 variations of canopy photosynthetic capacity. Specifically, COV can explain more
33 than 79% variations of canopy photosynthesis generated by changing leaf angle and
34 more than 84% variations of canopy photosynthesis generated by changing leaf area.
35 • As COV can be calculated in a high-throughput manner based on the canopy point
36 clouds, it can be used to evaluate canopy architecture in breeding and agronomic
37 research.

38

39 **Keywords:** Canopy photosynthesis, canopy architecture, 3D point clouds, high-
40 throughput phenotyping, phenomics, leaf segmentation, maize, ideotype.

41

42 The total word count for the main body of the text is 6432. The word count of
43 Introduction, Materials and Methods, Results, Discussion is 997, 3062, 1052 and 1320,
44 respectively. This paper includes 11 colour figures. The supporting material includes a
45 detailed description of 2 methods, 4 figures, 3 tables and 3 equations.

46

47

48

49

50

51

52

53

54

55

56

57

58 **1. Introduction**

59 The increase of world population and global climate change impose a major
60 challenge in global food security (Anderson *et al.*, 2020; Myers *et al.*, 2017; Ray *et al.*,
61 2012). A strategy to cope with the challenge is to breed higher-yielding, pest- and
62 disease-resistant and climate-smart crops (Cooper *et al.*, 2014; Furbank *et al.*, 2019;
63 Hickey *et al.*, 2019). Canopy architecture is a major yield determinant in cereals since
64 it influences light distribution, light interception, and correspondingly canopy
65 photosynthesis (Long *et al.*, 2006; Ort *et al.*, 2015; Zhu *et al.*, 2010). Leaf angle and
66 leaf area index (LAI) are two of the most important architectural traits influencing light
67 interception and canopy photosynthesis (Anderson and Denmead, 1969; Duncan *et al.*,
68 1967). Improving the synergistic effect of LAI and leaf angle distribution in different
69 canopy layers can improve canopy photosynthesis (Long *et al.*, 2006; Zhu *et al.*, 2010).
70 When LAI is low (e.g., less than three), canopies with more horizontal leaves can
71 intercept more light. When the LAI is high, an optimal canopy needs to have the top-
72 layer leaves more erect while the lower leaves gradually increase their leaf angle with
73 depth into the canopy. This architecture can avoid severe light saturation at the upper
74 part of the canopy and allow more light incident on lower layer leaves (Mantilla-Perez
75 and Salas Fernandez, 2017; Ort *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, the optimal leaf angle depends
76 on the leaf area index and leaf shape *etc.* So far, although the qualitative description of
77 the interaction or synergistic effects between LAI, leaf angle and leaf shape on canopy
78 photosynthesis have been intensively studied, quantifying the quality of such
79 synergistic effect remains a challenge.

80 The synergistic effect between LAI, leaf angle and leaf shape determines the crop
81 canopy photosynthesis and yield potential, hence it is implicitly used as ideotype
82 features for crops, such rice (Peng *et al.*, 1994) and maize (Mock and Pearce, 1975). So
83 far, the proposed crop ideotypes are usually composed of architectural features
84 extracted from high-yielding cultivars (Peng *et al.*, 2008), which are usually related to
85 improving canopy photosynthetic efficiency. However, their contributions to the
86 improved canopy photosynthesis cannot be quantified through the traditional empirical

87 feature extraction method.

88 Various theoretical and computational models have been developed to study
89 canopy photosynthesis and identify features controlling canopy photosynthesis. These
90 models include the big leaf model (Sellers *et al.*, 1996), the sunlit/shaded model (De
91 Pury and Farquhar, 1997), the multilayer model (Lemon *et al.*, 1971) and the three-
92 dimensional (3D) canopy photosynthetic model (Song *et al.*, 2013; Wang *et al.*, 2006;
93 Wen *et al.*, 2019). With the multilayer model, (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2017) showed that
94 optimizing soybean LAI can increase canopy photosynthesis and seed yield under
95 elevated CO₂ condition. The 3D canopy photosynthesis models have been used to study
96 the effects of changing canopy architectures (Chang *et al.*, 2019; Song *et al.*, 2013;
97 Zheng *et al.*, 2008), planting patterns (Wang *et al.*, 2017; B. Zhu *et al.*, 2020),
98 environmental factors (Burgess *et al.*, 2016; Song *et al.*, 2020) and physiological traits
99 (Burgess *et al.*, 2020; Foo *et al.*, 2020) on canopy photosynthesis. So far, large scale
100 application of these models to ideotype design is constrained by a lack of high
101 throughput methods of obtaining architectural features at the organ scale.

102 The traditional methods of building crop 3D models can be classified into two
103 categories. One is synthetic model which is built with manual measurements of canopy
104 architectural traits (e.g., leaf length, leaf width, leaf angle and plant height) for each
105 organ of a plant or to use 2D imaging technology to reconstruct 3D canopy models
106 synthetically (Chang *et al.*, 2019; España *et al.*, 1999; Song *et al.*, 2013). The another
107 is point clouds model, which is developed based on 3D point clouds obtained with
108 different methods, including 3D digitization technologies (Sinoquet *et al.*, 1991; Wang
109 *et al.*, 2018; Zheng *et al.*, 2011), depth cameras (e.g., time-of-flight (ToF) cameras)
110 (Jiang *et al.*, 2016; Ma *et al.*, 2019; McCormick *et al.*, 2016), light detection and ranging
111 (LiDAR) (S. Jin *et al.*, 2021; Perez *et al.*, 2018; Sun *et al.*, 2018) and image-based 3D
112 reconstruction techniques (e.g., structure from motion and multi-view stereo, SFM-
113 MVS) (Duan *et al.*, 2016; Hui *et al.*, 2018; Pound *et al.*, 2014). The synthetic model
114 can be easily manipulated *in silico* to study the influence of different canopy
115 architectures on canopy photosynthesis and to conduct ideotype design (Song *et al.*,

116 2013), but, as stated earlier, it is time-consuming to measure plant architectural traits.
117 By contrast, the point clouds model can be obtained efficiently; however, such methods
118 cannot conduct *in silico* perturbation analysis.

119 Among different methods to develop point clouds model, LiDAR, which is the
120 most accurate method and less influenced by environmental conditions, has been used
121 to estimate diverse phenotypic traits non-invasively (e.g., plant height, leaf area
122 distribution, blade length, blade width and stem length *etc.*) (Su *et al.*, 2018; Thapa *et al.*,
123 *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2018). After the 3D point clouds data are obtained, the individual
124 organs, e.g., stem, leaf, spike, *etc.*, need to be segmented to extract detail architectural
125 traits. Various algorithms have been developed to segment stem and leaves, such as
126 region growing based algorithm (Jin *et al.*, 2019; Yang *et al.*, 2016), tensor-based
127 algorithm (Elnashef *et al.*, 2019), clustering method based on the surface feature
128 (Wahabzada *et al.*, 2015) and skeleton-based approaches (Wu *et al.*, 2019; C. Zhu *et al.*,
129 2020). These algorithms showed excellent performance on relatively simple plant
130 architectures. However, these algorithms need to be individually tuned for specific plant
131 architecture, and importantly, these models cannot deal with the plant canopies with
132 overlapped leaves.

133 In this study, we develop a robust method to accurately extract maize canopy
134 architectural traits based on point clouds data, which is used to develop a new method
135 to conduct perturbation analysis and crop ideotype design with point cloud data. With
136 this new method, we propose an effective parameter which reflects the synergistic effect
137 of LAI and leaf angle distribution on canopy photosynthetic capacity.

138

139 **2. Materials and methods**

140 **2.1 Plant materials and experiments**

141 The experiment was conducted at the Songjiang experimental station of the Institute
142 of Plant Physiology and Ecology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), Shanghai,
143 China (30°56'44" N, 121°8'1" E) in 2020. Three maize (*Zea mays*) inbred lines (cultivars)
144 with different plant architectures, A619, B73 and W64A, were planted in pots. The pots

145 were kept outdoors randomly with a row and column distance of 40cm. The ambient
146 environmental data was attached in Supplementary Table S1. The volume of the pot is
147 20 L. Two seeds were sown in each pot, and one plant was kept at the seedling stage.
148 15 biological replicates were grown, and eight of them were used for measurements.
149 The soil in pots was a mixture of garden soil, peat soil and vermiculite with a volume
150 ratio of 5:3:2. Fertilizer (12.2g N, 3g P₂O₅ and 3g K₂O for each pot) was applied before
151 sowing.

152 A terrestrial LiDAR (light detection and ranging), FARO Focus S70 (FARO, Lake
153 Mary, Florida, USA), was used to obtain plant architectures. The terrestrial LiDAR
154 scanned three target plants at four different stations. Six calibration balls were arranged
155 at different positions for later point clouds registration and connection of the different
156 scan stations as an integrated point cloud data. Plant architectures were collected at 37,
157 44, 52 and 58 days after sowing (DAS) with the terrestrial LiDAR. After 3D plant
158 architecture information was collected, plant architectural features including leaf base
159 height, leaf length, and leaf width at different positions (0, 1/4, 1/2 and 3/4 of leaf length
160 from leaf base) along a leaf were manually measured with a ruler for all the cultivars.

161 The physiological parameters of plants were collected at 58 DAS. Leaf chlorophyll
162 content was quantified with a chlorophyll metre SPAD502Plus (Konica Minolta, Japan).
163 For each leaf, the average value of six measurements at different positions along the
164 leaf was recorded. To predict the leaf reflectance and transmittance from SPAD values,
165 leaf reflectance and transmittance spectrum of photosynthetic active radiation (PAR)
166 (400-700 nm) were measured with integrating sphere and spectrometer (Ocean Optics,
167 Dunedin, Florida, USA). Leaf reflectance (R) and transmittance (T) are the weighted
168 averages of PAR calculated according to (Eqn. 1-2) (Song *et al.*, 2017). R_i is the
169 reflectance of wavelength i . I_i is incident solar PAR at wavelength i . T_i is the
170 transmittance of wavelength i .

171

172

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=400}^{700} R_i * I_i}{\sum_{i=400}^{700} I_i} \quad (1)$$

173

$$T = \frac{\sum_{i=400}^{700} T_i * I_i}{\sum_{i=400}^{700} I_i} \quad (2)$$

174

175 Leaf photosynthetic light response curves (A-Q curve) were measured using an
176 LI-6400XT (LI-COR, Lincoln, Nebraska, USA). A-Q curves of leaves at the upper and
177 lower layers were measured. The upper and lower leaves were defined by the leaf
178 position. If the total plant height is H, then, leaves below H/2 are regarded as lower
179 leaves and leaves above H/2 are regarded as upper leaves. For each cultivar, five upper
180 leaves and five lower leaves from different plants were measured for A-Q curves. The
181 light response curves of photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate (A-Q) curves were measured
182 between 9 am and 4 pm with LI-6400. The photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD)
183 changed from 2000 to 0 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (by steps of 2000, 1600, 1200, 1000, 800, 600,
184 400, 300, 200, 150, 100, 50, 0), and for each step, a constant waiting time of 2 mins 30
185 s was applied before data logging. The block temperature of leaf chamber was set to be
186 33 °C (37 DAS), 33 °C (44 DAS), 33 °C (52 DAS) and 30 °C (58 DAS) according to
187 the ambient temperature on the day of measurements at different developmental stages.
188 The humidity of the leaf chamber was not controlled, and the humidity in the leaf
189 chamber was 51~80% (37 DAS), 57~80% (44 DAS), 47~64% (52 DAS), 60~81% (58
190 DAS). A-Q curves were fitted by a non-rectangular hyperbola model (Eqn. 3) (Thornley,
191 2002). $A(I)$ is leaf photosynthesis rate under the incident light intensity(I). P_{max} is leaf
192 photosynthetic rate under the saturate incident light intensity. ϕ is photosynthetic
193 efficiency and θ represents the convexity of the A-Q curve.

194

$$195 \quad A(I) = \frac{\phi I + P_{max} - \sqrt{(\phi I + P_{max})^2 - 4\theta\phi I P_{max}}}{2\theta} \quad (3)$$

196

197 **2.2 Point clouds registration and denoising**

198 The supporting software of the scanner SCENE 2019 (FARO, Lake Mary, Florida,
199 USA) was used to register original point clouds. The target plant point clouds were
200 segmented from original point clouds (Fig. 1a), including plant, soil, pot and noise
201 through several steps. Firstly, the soil was separated (Fig. 1b) by extracting the soil
202 surface by *pcfitplane* function implemented in MATLAB (MathWorks, USA; version

203 R2020b), which uses M-estimator sample consensus (MSAC) algorithm (Torr and
204 Zisserman, 2000). The MSAC algorithm fits a plane to point clouds with a maximum
205 allowable distance (5 cm in this study) from an inlier point to the plane. Then the target
206 point clouds (Fig. 1c) were extracted from the remaining point clouds (Fig. 1b) by the
207 *pcdenoise* and *pcsegdist* function implemented in MATLAB. The *pcdenoise* was used
208 to remove outliers which are 0.3 standard deviation away from the mean distance. The
209 mean distance is the average distance of each point from its nearest neighbours (50
210 neighbours were used in this study). Then the *pcsegdist* function was used to remove
211 the larger outliers (the remaining point clouds of the pot) according to a Euclidean
212 distance threshold (5 mm was used in this study).

213

214 **2.3 Plant organ segmentation**

215 In this study, a new method based on the skeleton and region growing algorithm was
216 developed to segment plant organs, i.e., leaves and a stem. Firstly, the denoised point
217 clouds of each plant were processed with a Laplacian based method (Cao *et al.*, 2010)
218 to generate plant skeleton points, a connectivity matrix of skeleton points and an
219 incidence matrix between point clouds and skeleton points (Fig. 2a). The Laplacian
220 based method is a contraction operation that is designed to work on point clouds via
221 local Delaunay triangulation and topological thinning. Secondly, a region growing
222 algorithm (Rabbani *et al.*, 2006) was used to divide point clouds into clusters (Fig. 2d)
223 according to the curvatures and angles of the normal vectors changing along the organ
224 surface. The plant organ segmentation includes three parts, i.e., leaf skeleton extraction,
225 classification of point clouds clusters and unclassified clusters merging. Reference leaf
226 point clouds (Fig. 2c) were obtained from the plant point clouds according to the leaf
227 skeletons. According to reference leaf point clouds and angles between clusters and
228 stem direction, small clusters (Fig. 2d) were classified to organ point clouds (Fig. 2e)
229 and unclassified point clouds. The unclassified point clouds were classified into clusters
230 by the region growing method (Fig. 2f). The larger clusters from unclassified point
231 clouds were merged into organ point clouds (Fig. 2g) according to the similarity of

232 normal and curvature of points between the larger cluster and neighbouring organ point
233 clouds. Finally, the remaining clusters were merged into organ point clouds by a
234 Euclidean distance-based method (C. Zhu *et al.*, 2020) (Fig. 2h) (see Methods S1 for
235 details).

236 The accuracy of plant organ segmentation was defined as the number of correct
237 classification point clouds divided by the number of all point clouds, which was used
238 to evaluate the performance of the new algorithm.

239

240 **2.4 Extraction of leaf architectural traits**

241 After organ point clouds were obtained, leaf traits were extracted based on the leaf
242 point clouds. Leaf length, maximal leaf width, leaf angle, leaf area, leaf smoothness,
243 and leaf flatness were obtained. To characterize leaf traits in a high throughput way, the
244 redundant points were removed from the leaf point clouds with a voxelized grid
245 approach with the *pcdownsample* function of Matlab. Specifically, firstly, a set of small
246 3D voxels were created in the space of the point clouds, then the centroid of each voxel
247 is used to represent all the points in the voxel (Han *et al.*, 2017). Finally, the region
248 growth algorithm was used to remove outliers.

249 The leaf base point is defined as the closest point to the stem point clouds. The leaf
250 midrib was rotated to the positive direction of the x-axis around the leaf base point (Fig.
251 3a). The rotated angle was decided by the main direction of plant point clouds in the
252 horizontal plane (XOY plane in 3A) estimated by the Principal Component Analysis
253 (PCA) algorithm. The leaf tip point was found mainly by three steps. First, leaf point
254 clouds were divided into two segments, with the Part 1 from the leaf base to the highest
255 point of the leaf and Part 2 from the highest point of the leaf to the leaf tip. Then the
256 *pcsegdist* function was used to find the outliers according to a Euclidean distance in
257 Part 1. If there is no outlier in Part 1, the lowest point in Part 2 was regarded as the leaf
258 tip point (Fig. 3a); otherwise, the lowest point in the outliers in Part 1 was regarded as
259 the leaf tip point (Fig. 3a, sub-figure). Leaf length (Fig. 3a, red line) was the distance
260 of the shortest path between the leaf base and the leaf tip. Leaf width (Fig. 3a, yellow

261 line) was the distance of the shortest path between the points in two leaf edges. The
 262 shortest path was calculated by the Dijkstra method (Dijkstra, 1959) which is an
 263 algorithm for finding the shortest paths between nodes in a graph. Leaf width at 0, 1/4,
 264 1/2 and 3/4 of leaf length from the leaf base was extracted. Leaf angle was defined as
 265 the angle between the vector from the base point to the point of the leaf midrib at 1/3
 266 of leaf length from the leaf base and the vertical direction (Fig. 3a). Smooth leaf edges,
 267 which is defined as the leaf edge with the distortion and undulation removed, were
 268 estimated by an empirical leaf shape model (Dornbusch *et al.*, 2011) based on the
 269 calculated leaf length and four leaf width values. The smooth leaf edge (Fig. 3a, blue
 270 line; Eqn. 4) was generated by the path of leaf length (Fig. 3a, red line):

$$271 \quad (x_s, y_s, z_s) = (x_p, y_p, z_p) \pm (0, 0.5 * LW_p, 0) \quad (4)$$

272 where the x_s, y_s, z_s are coordinates of points of the smooth leaf edge, x_p, y_p, z_p are
 273 coordinates of points in the path of leaf length, LW_p is the leaf width at the
 274 corresponding point in the path of leaf length.

275 In this study, two new parameters were used to evaluate leaf flatness (L_f) and leaf
 276 smoothness (L_s). Leaf flatness was defined as the ratio between the area surrounded by
 277 the projected smooth leaf edge (PA_e) and leaf area estimated by leaf shape model (LA_e ;
 278 Eqn. 5). Leaf smoothness (L_s) was defined as the ratio between the projected area of
 279 point clouds (PA_p) and the area surrounded by the projected smooth leaf edge (PA_e ; Eqn.
 280 6).

281

$$282 \quad L_f = \frac{PA_e}{LA_e} \quad (5)$$

$$283 \quad L_s = \frac{PA_p}{PA_e} \quad (6)$$

284

285 The leaf area was estimated by a meshed leaf model consisting of triangles. The leaf
 286 area (LA) was calculated by the sum of triangle areas (s ; Eqn. 7). Point clouds were
 287 transferred to the meshed leaf model based on a Crust-based method (Liu *et al.*, 2021)
 288 which firstly adopts the Crust method (Amenta *et al.*, 1998) to triangulation and then

289 uses a statistic method to filter abnormal facets (i.e. triangles). The Crust method is a
290 classical surface reconstruction method based on Delaunay triangulation and 3D
291 Voronoi diagram of point clouds.

292

$$293 \quad LA = \sum_{i=1}^n s_i \quad (7)$$

294

295 The accuracy of calculated leaf architectural traits was verified through comparison
296 with experimental data. Leaf length, maximal leaf width and leaf area of precisely
297 segmented leaves were used for the verification. The calculated leaf length and maximal
298 leaf width were compared with manual measurements. The calculated leaf area was
299 compared to the leaf area estimated from the measured leaf length and leaf width based
300 on an empirical leaf shape model (Dornbusch *et al.*, 2011). The coefficient of
301 determination (R^2) and root mean square error ($RMSE$) were used to compare the
302 calculated value and measured value.

303

304 **2.6 Analyses of the impacts of plant architectural traits on canopy photosynthesis.**

305 We developed a new ideotype design method based on point clouds and conducted
306 a series of *in silico* experiments to analyse the impacts of different architectural features
307 on canopy photosynthesis. Four plants without any broken leaves were selected in each
308 cultivar at 58 DAS for *in silico* experiments. The architecture of selected plants in each
309 cultivar was changed by changing the upper and lower leaf architecture via changing
310 the leaf area (Fig. 4a and b) and leaf angle (Fig. 4c) one by one, as the leaf architectural
311 traits of maize in the upper and lower canopies are under independent genetic control
312 (Zhang *et al.*, 2017). The leaves with a leaf base higher than 1/2 plant height (the 99.9th
313 percentile of the points is defined as the plant height) were considered as upper leaves
314 and the other leaves were regarded as lower leaves. The leaf area change was
315 implemented by changing leaf length (Fig. 4a) and leaf width (Fig. 4b). The percentage
316 changes of the leaf length and the leaf width are -40%, -20%, 0, 20%, 40%. The
317 percentage changes of the leaf angle depend on the original leaf angle. If the leaf angle

318 of an individual leaf decreases to 0 degrees, the leaf angle of the individual leaf will
319 stay unchanged rather than becoming a negative value. When leaf angles of 80%
320 individual leaves become 0 degrees, we defined the current percentage change as the
321 lowest percentage change. The highest percentage change was obtained similarly. When
322 leaf angles of 80% individual leaves are equal to 90 degrees, we defined the current
323 percentage change as the highest percentage change. Five percentage changes were set
324 between the lowest and highest percentage changes with an equal interval. The reason
325 why we chose 80% as a threshold is that the leaf angles vary greatly in a plant. If we
326 chose 100% as the threshold, the interval of the percentage change for the leaf angle
327 would be too big to build reasonable canopies. Changing leaf length (Fig. 4a), leaf width
328 (Fig. 4b) and leaf angle (Fig. 4c) were implemented by changing the coordinates of leaf
329 point clouds (see Methods S2 for details). The changed leaf point clouds were
330 assembled into the changed plant point clouds (Fig. 4d) and used to construct a canopy
331 model to calculate the canopy photosynthesis rate.

332

333 **2.7 Canopy model construction and canopy photosynthesis rate calculation**

334 Based on the plant point clouds, surface reconstruction was conducted to generate
335 meshed plants (Fig. 4e) consisting of a set of triangles according to a Crust-based
336 method (Liu *et al.*, 2021). The four selected meshed plants with the same plant
337 architectural change were used to generate virtual canopies with 4×4 plants (Fig. 4f)
338 with each selected meshed plant used 4 times. Four different meshed plants were used
339 for the central 2×2 plants and the other plants surrounding the central plants are
340 randomly arranged. According to the principle of random number generation, three
341 random matrices of plant positions in the virtual canopy were generated to minimize
342 the compounding effect of plant arrangements on canopy photosynthesis. Since plant
343 orientations in a canopy also affect canopy photosynthesis, three random matrices were
344 generated to simulate different plant orientations in each plant arrangements. The plants
345 in the virtual canopy were rotated around plant bases according to values in the random
346 matrices. In this study, we assume that the random matrices of plant positions and plant

347 orientations are the same for each treatment. The plant density of virtual canopy was
 348 set as 8 (plant distance: 22 cm; row distance: 55 cm), 10 (plant distance: 20 cm; row
 349 distance: 50 cm), 12 (plant distance: 18 cm; row distance: 46 cm) plants/m² according
 350 to the optimal maize plant density in different geographic location (Xu *et al.*, 2017).
 351 The central 4 plants in a canopy (Fig. 4f; plants within the blue voxel) was used to
 352 simulate the light distribution based on a ray-tracing software *fastTracer* (Song *et al.*,
 353 2013). In this software, when a light ray hits the boundary of the central canopy
 354 composed of these 4 plants, this light ray is moved to the opposite side of the central
 355 canopy. Therefore, the boundary effect is avoided. The ground area of the central
 356 canopy (S_g ; Eqn. 8) was calculated by the row spacing (d_r) multiplied by the plant
 357 spacing (d_p) and plant number (4 plants).

358

$$359 \quad S_g = d_r * d_p * 4 \quad (8)$$

360

361 The ratio between direct solar radiation and diffuse radiation changes with cloud
 362 cover. In this study, we assume the total radiation includes 70 % direct radiation and
 363 30 % diffuse radiation. The simulation was conducted on 58 DAS (September 17th 2020,
 364 Shanghai, 30°56'44" N, 121°8'1" E) from 6 am to 6 pm with a time interval of one hour.
 365 Leaf transmittance and reflectance were calculated based on the SPAD value of all
 366 leaves with regression equations relating SPAD value with absorbance and reflectance
 367 (Eqn. S1–S3, data in Table S2) since chlorophyll concentration is positively related to
 368 leaf absorbance and reflectance (Blackmer *et al.*, 1994; Earl and Tollenaar, 1997). After
 369 simulations, the daily light interception per unit ground (LI ; Eqn.9), the daily net canopy
 370 photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate per unit ground (A_c ; Eqn.11) and the light use efficiency
 371 (LUE ; Eqn.12) were computed.

372

$$373 \quad LI = \frac{\int_{t=6}^{18} (\sum_{i=1}^n s_i * IF_i) dt}{S_g} \quad (9)$$

$$374 \quad R_d = 12 * 3600 * \sum_{i=1}^n s_i * A(0) \quad (10)$$

$$375 \quad A_c = \frac{\int_{t=6}^{18} (\sum_{i=1}^n s_i * A(IF_i)) dt - R_d}{S_g} \quad (11)$$

376
$$LUE = \frac{A_c}{LI} \quad (12)$$

377

378 where IF_i is incident PPFD of facet i . S_i is the area of facet i , n is the number of facets.
379 R_d is the dark respiration rate. $A(0)$ is leaf photosynthesis rate under 0 incident PPFD.

380 The fitted A-Q curves were used to calculate leaf photosynthesis rates for
381 individual triangles of leaves and the canopy photosynthesis rate was calculated as the
382 sum of photosynthetic CO₂ uptake divided by the ground area. Three A-Q curves for
383 upper leaves and three A-Q curves for lower leaves were fitted to each cultivar to study
384 the impacts of canopy architecture on canopy photosynthesis under different A-Q
385 curves.

386

387 **2.8 Calculation of canopy architectural traits**

388 The canopy architectural traits including leaf area index, facet angle, canopy
389 coverage and canopy occupation volume were calculated. The leaf area index was
390 represented by canopy leaf area per unit ground area. Facet angle was the mean angle
391 between facets and the vertical direction, which represents leaf erectness. To calculate
392 the canopy coverage and canopy occupation volume, the canopy model was voxelized
393 (one voxel/1 cm thickness; Fig. 5a), and the voxels containing triangles of the canopy
394 model are regarded as the occupied voxels (Fig. 5, yellow voxels). The total volume of
395 the occupied voxels is the canopy occupation volume. The canopy coverage is the ratio
396 of occupied area and the area of the horizontal plane (Fig. 5c).

397

398 **3 Results**

399 **3.1 Extraction and comparison of plant architecture among three cultivars.**

400 We obtained high-quality point clouds for all three cultivars (W64A, A619, B73)
401 from 37 DAS to 58 DAS (Fig. 6). The new skeleton and region growing algorithm-
402 based method was adopted to segment plant organs for three cultivars at all growth
403 stages. The accuracy of organ segmentation was more than 97% (Table. S3). The
404 method can precisely segment plant organs in most cases. The error of organ

405 segmentation mainly appears in two main cases, i.e., when the leaf is very close to the
406 stem (Fig. 6, B73 at 52 and 58 DAS) and when the leaf was not separated from the stem.
407 And the tassels were regarded as different organs (Fig. 6, A619 at 58 DAS).

408 The accuracy of the reconstructed plant models was evaluated by the difference
409 between the calculated leaf traits of precisely segmented leaves and leaf traits obtained
410 manually. The calculated leaf length, maximum leaf width and leaf area of the precisely
411 segmented leaves were in good agreements with the measured leaf length, measured
412 maximum leaf width and reference leaf area estimated by the measured leaf length and
413 leaf width based on an empirical leaf shape model (leaf length: $R^2 = 0.89$ and RMSE =
414 3.98 cm; maximum leaf width: $R^2 = 0.76$ and RMSE = 0.92 cm; and leaf area: $R^2 = 0.86$
415 and RMSE = 44.13 cm²; Fig. 7a, 7b and 7c). There is no difference in the accuracy of
416 leaf length, maximum leaf width and leaf area between leaves in the lower and upper
417 part of plants.

418 The plant architectural parameters differed dramatically among three cultivars at
419 four growth stages (Fig.6 and Fig. 8). At 58 DAS, the upper part leaf angle and leaf
420 smoothness for three cultivars were significantly different. For the upper part leaf angle,
421 W64A had more horizontal leaves and B73 had more vertical leaves. For the upper part
422 leaf smoothness, leaves in B73 were smoother than leaves in other cultivars and the
423 leaves in A619 had more undulation than other cultivars. On top of this, although there
424 was no significant difference in the upper part leaf area among the three cultivars, the
425 leaf of W64A had a wider leaf width and shorter leaf length than other cultivars (Fig.
426 8). Besides the difference in plant architecture, the A-Q curves of the three cultivars
427 were also different (Fig. S1). The photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate of W64A was lower
428 than other cultivars, especially in the upper part, while that of A619 was higher than
429 other cultivars both in the lower and upper part.

430

431 **3.2 The influence of different canopy architectural traits on photosynthesis and** 432 **the relationship between canopy architectural traits and canopy photosynthesis.**

433 Leaf area can be changed by changing leaf length and leaf width. The architectural

434 change in the upper part of the canopy had a greater impact on canopy photosynthesis
435 than that in the lower part of the canopy (Fig. S2). When the coverage rate of the canopy
436 was lower than 0.92, the canopy photosynthesis increased linearly with leaf area (Fig.
437 S2 and S3). Too large or too small upper leaf angle was not beneficial for canopy
438 photosynthesis, the optimal canopy photosynthesis of virtual canopy based on changed
439 upper leaf angle did not appear in the virtual canopy with the smallest or the biggest
440 upper leaf angle (Fig. S2).

441 We simulate five virtual canopies (VC1 to VC5) with different upper layer leaf
442 angles (UA). From VC1 to VC5, the upper layer leaf changed from vertical (small UA)
443 to horizontal (large UA) while the leaf area index kept constant as leaf length and width
444 were not changed. When the upper leaf angle was changed (Fig. 9g), the canopy
445 photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate, the canopy light interception and canopy architectural
446 traits were changed though the leaf area index remained unchanged (Fig. 9). With the
447 increase in upper leaf angle, the canopy light interception (Fig. 9d), facet angle (Fig. 9f)
448 and canopy coverage increased (Fig. 9e), while the leaf area index was unchanged (Fig.
449 9c). Only the canopy occupation volume showed the same trend as the canopy
450 photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate with a decrease in the biggest upper part leaf angle
451 (Virtual canopy 5; Fig. 9a and b).

452 For the relationship between daily canopy photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate and
453 canopy architectural traits of all virtual canopies, the canopy occupation volume was
454 the architectural trait that explains the most variations in canopy photosynthesis
455 generated by changing architectures, e.g., it explained more than 79% and 84% of the
456 variations in canopy photosynthesis generated by changing leaf angle and leaf area,
457 respectively (Fig. 10 and Fig. S4). By comparison, the leaf area index explained more
458 than 80% of variations of canopy photosynthesis generated by changing leaf area;
459 however, it cannot explain the variations of canopy photosynthesis generated by
460 changing leaf angle. The high R² between leaf area and canopy photosynthesis was
461 attributed to the large variations in leaf area among different cultivars and planting
462 densities (Fig. 10 and Fig. S4). The canopy coverage had a significant linear

463 relationship with canopy photosynthesis in canopies obtained by changing leaf area.
464 However, there was a significant difference between cultivars in the linear relationships
465 between canopy photosynthesis and canopy coverage. Canopy coverage also cannot
466 explain the variations of canopy photosynthesis generated by changing leaf angle (Fig.
467 10 and Fig. S4). The facet angle cannot well explain the variations of canopy
468 photosynthesis generated by changing either leaf angle or leaf area (Fig. 10 and Fig.
469 S4).

470 The reasons why canopy occupation volume can indicate canopy photosynthesis
471 better than other architectural traits mainly include two aspects. First, canopy
472 occupation volume can indicate overlaps between leaves. Overlapped leaves had
473 smaller canopy occupation volume than leaves that were spread out (Fig. 11a), while
474 the light interception of overlapped leaves was smaller as well (Fig. 11b). Secondly, the
475 change of canopy occupation volume can reflect the change of canopy photosynthesis
476 generated by changing leaf angle. When the leaf angle was close to 90 or 0 degrees, the
477 canopy occupation volume was smaller than that when the leaf angle was intermediate
478 between 0 and 90 degrees since leaves with intermediate leaf angle have less possibility
479 to overlap with other leaves and stem (Fig. 11c). Less overlap between leaves enabled
480 the canopy to have higher canopy photosynthesis (Fig. 11d).

481

482 **4. Discussion**

483 In this study, a robust algorithm to accurately extract maize canopy architectural
484 traits based on point clouds data is developed. We further developed a new method
485 which enables perturbation analysis and crop ideotype design method with point cloud
486 data. With this new method, we show that the canopy occupation volume reflects the
487 synergistic effect of LAI and leaf angle distribution on canopy photosynthetic capacity
488 and hence can be used as a novel parameter to represent canopy photosynthetic capacity.

489

490 **4.1 Development of a robust algorithm to extract architectural parameters from** 491 **point cloud data to tackle a major challenge in the current high-throughput**

492 **phenotyping research**

493 Obtaining architectural parameters for plants represents a major research challenge
494 of current plant phenomics research. Previous studies used algorithms to segment a
495 stem and leaves, especially on relatively simple maize plant architecture (Elnashef *et*
496 *al.*, 2019; Jin *et al.*, 2018; C. Zhu *et al.*, 2020). However, the parameters of these
497 algorithms need to be carefully tuned to enable accurate segmentation and these
498 methods cannot deal with the plant model with overlapped leaves. In this study, a new
499 skeleton and region growing based method was developed to segment a stem and leaves,
500 which could be applied to segment overlapped leaves. Although there are still some
501 parameters used in this algorithm, in this study, the same set of parameter values can be
502 used to segment stem and leaves among three different cultivars at four growth stages,
503 and gain an accuracy of segmentation higher than 97% for all treatments (Fig. 6 and
504 Table. S2). This method can also be used to segment stem and leaves in other crops
505 which have similar plant architecture with maize (e.g., sorghum). For plants with leaves
506 being extremely close to the stem, new algorithm development is still in need.

507 In this study, besides developing new algorithms to segment stem and leaves, a
508 new method was also developed to extract leaf length based on point cloud data.
509 Generally, the first step during the automatic extraction of leaf length is to find the leaf
510 tip and leaf base. Recent research considers the farthest point to the leaf base as the leaf
511 tip (Duan *et al.*, 2016; B. Zhu *et al.*, 2020). Though this method can be used to extract
512 leaf length for leaves with relatively plane leaves, it cannot find the right leaf tip in
513 leaves with large curvature. This study developed a method to extract leaf length for
514 leaves with different shapes and curvatures with high accurately ($R^2=0.89$, $RMSE=3.98$
515 cm , $N=348$, Fig.7). On top of this, we proposed new methods to quantify leaf
516 smoothness and flatness. In summary, here we developed a set of algorithms to extract
517 plant architectural parameters accurately.

518 Compared to previous indoor maize phenotyping pipeline (Cabrera-Bosquet *et al.*,
519 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2017), the pipeline proposed here can be used to effectively derive
520 a 3D plant model which can be directly used by a ray-tracing algorithm to simulate the

521 canopy light environment and hence canopy photosynthesis (Fig. 7 and 8). Although
522 the photosynthetic traits (e.g., leaf transmittance, leaf reflectance and A-Q curves) were
523 estimated based on the measured data, these photosynthetic traits can be estimated using
524 hyperspectral reflectance data since hyperspectral reflectance data can be used to
525 calculate photosynthetic properties (Meacham-Hensold *et al.*, 2020; Silva-Perez *et al.*,
526 2018). In the future, integration of the photosynthetic traits estimated using
527 hyperspectral reflectance with the 3D canopy photosynthesis model based on point
528 clouds data can enable a high-throughput quantification of canopy photosynthesis,
529 which can be facilitate dissect the key functional loci and obtain rich data set to support
530 the development and validation of process-based crop models.

531

532 **4.2 A new method for ideotype design and perturbation analysis using point** 533 **cloud data**

534 Ideotype design plays a crucial role in crop breeding. For example, increasing
535 plant density together with optimized crop architecture has been crucial for the
536 improvement of maize yield over decades (Fischer and Edmeades, 2010; Hammer *et*
537 *al.*, 2009; Ma *et al.*, 2014; Pendleton *et al.*, 1968; Tian *et al.*, 2011). Recently, (Zhang
538 *et al.*, 2017) found leaf angle is under independent genetic control at different levels of
539 a canopy which provides an opportunity to design and genetically manipulate
540 individual layers to gain higher energy conversion efficiency. However, identifying
541 ideotypes remains a major challenge. 3D canopy photosynthesis models which combine
542 accurate three-dimensional canopy reconstruction and the ray-tracing algorithm can be
543 used to accurately estimate canopy light distribution, light interception and
544 photosynthetic capacity (Song *et al.*, 2020; Townsend *et al.*, 2018; Wen *et al.*, 2019;
545 Zheng *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, such a method in principle can be used to design crop
546 ideotypes, as shown by earlier work on studying the combined effects of different
547 architectural parameters on canopy photosynthesis in rice (Chang *et al.*, 2019; Song *et*
548 *al.*, 2013). However, such a method requires time-consuming data collection for
549 parameterization, especially for plants with complex architectures. In this study, a point

550 clouds based ideotype design method is proposed (Fig. 4), which can change the leaf
551 architectural traits, including leaf shape, leaf area and leaf angle, without complex
552 parameterization. This method provides a new strategy to identify ideotype and fills the
553 gap of maize ideotype design.

554

555 **4.3 Canopy occupation volume as a novel parameter representing the canopy** 556 **photosynthetic capacity**

557 Leaf angle and LAI are two major factors determining canopy photosynthesis.
558 These two factors interact non-linearly to determine canopy photosynthesis jointly.
559 High canopy photosynthesis requires a proper combination of LAI and leaf angle.
560 Many earlier studies identified sets of combinations of LAI and leaf angle for better
561 photosynthetic efficiency. For example, combining more upright leaves and a greater
562 LAI increases the canopy light interception capacity and yield potential (Duvick,
563 2005; Lauer *et al.*, 2012; Lee and Tollenaar, 2007). Crop ideotypes usually need
564 smaller leaf angles on the upper layers of a canopy, intermediate leaf angles at the
565 middle layers of a canopy and large leaf angles at the lower layers of a canopy (Ku *et*
566 *al.*, 2010; Long *et al.*, 2006; Ort *et al.*, 2015; Zhu *et al.*, 2010).

567 So far, there is no single parameter that can be used to quantify their interactions,
568 and hence it is difficult to directly evaluate the goodness of a particular combination of
569 LAI and leaf angle. We show that the common canopy architectural traits, such as leaf
570 area index and canopy coverage, and a newly proposed canopy architectural trait, mean
571 facet angle (Hou *et al.*, 2016; Perez *et al.*, 2019; Zheng *et al.*, 2008), cannot explain and
572 quantify the synergistic effect of leaf area and leaf angle on canopy photosynthesis (Fig.
573 10 and Fig. S4). The canopy occupation volume proposed in this study however can
574 explain more than 79% variations of canopy photosynthesis generated by changing leaf
575 angle and more than 84% variations of canopy photosynthesis generated by changing
576 leaf area (Fig. 10 and Fig. S4). The reason why canopy occupation volume can be used
577 to evaluate canopy photosynthesis variation caused by altering canopy architectural
578 parameters is that this parameter indicates the change of effective photosynthetic area

579 (Fig. 11). The canopy occupation volume can reflect overlaps between leaves or
580 between leaf and stem.

581 Crop architectures show dynamic changes along different developmental stages;
582 furthermore, canopy architecture are greatly influenced by genetic variation and
583 environmental and management practices (Alam *et al.*, 2014; Chenu *et al.*, 2018; Keller
584 *et al.*, 2019). Efficient methods to evaluate these diverse canopy architectures will
585 facilitate the future selection of better architectures for greater photosynthetic capacity
586 and hence crop yield potential. The canopy occupation volume reported in this study
587 represents an effective metric to represents how “good” is the canopy architecture in
588 terms of the canopy photosynthesis rate. With the various platforms to acquire 3D
589 canopy architecture in the field (X. Jin *et al.*, 2021; Lei *et al.*, 2019; Salas Fernandez *et*
590 *al.*, 2017; Virlet *et al.*, 2017), the method developed in this study hence can be used as
591 a generic method to screen the canopy for those with higher COV to support high
592 throughput evaluation of canopy architectures and hence support future of crop
593 breeding.

594

595 **Acknowledgements**

596

597 This work is supported by Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (OPP1172157),
598 National Key Research and Development Program (2020YFA0907600) and National
599 Natural Science Foundation of China (31970378). We acknowledge Xinyu Liu and all
600 members of plant systems biology in CEMPS for the valuable suggestions.

601

602 **Data availability**

603

604 The source code is available for research and teaching purposes on request from the
605 authors. The methods can be freely used for academic purposes. For commercial
606 purposes, a special license is required. These new methods are freely accessible on
607 GitHub (<https://github.com/FusangLiu/Maize-phenotyping-methods-ba-sed-on-point->

608 clouds).

609 **Author contributions**

610 F. L. developed the new pipelines, analysed the data. and interpreted results. X. Z.,
611 Q.S. and F. L. conceived the research. F.L. wrote the paper with the inputs of all
612 authors. X. Z. and Q.S. revised the paper. Q.S., J. Z., L. M., H. B. and Y. H.
613 coordinated and performed the field experimentation.

614

615

616

617

618

619

620

621

622

623

624

625

626

627

628

629

630

631

632

633

634

635

636

637

638 **Reference**

639 **Alam MM, Hammer GL, van Oosterom EJ, Cruickshank AW, Hunt CH, Jordan**
640 **DR.** 2014. A physiological framework to explain genetic and environmental regulation
641 of tillering in sorghum. *New Phytologist* **203**: 155-167.

642 **Amenta N, Bern M, Kamvysselis M.** 1998. A new Voronoi-based surface
643 reconstruction algorithm. *Proceedings of the 25th annual conference on Computer*
644 *graphics and interactive techniques.* New York, NY, United States: Association for
645 Computing Machinery, 415-421.

646 **Anderson MC, Denmead O.** 1969. Short Wave Radiation on Inclined Surfaces in
647 Model Plant Communities 1. *Agronomy Journal* **61**: 867-872.

648 **Anderson R, Bayer PE, Edwards D.** 2020. Climate change and the need for
649 agricultural adaptation. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology* **56**: 197-202.

650 **Blackmer TM, Schepers JS, Varvel GE.** 1994. Light reflectance compared with other
651 nitrogen stress measurements in corn leaves. *Agronomy Journal* **86**: 934-938.

652 **Burgess AJ, Herman T, Ali A, Murchie EH.** 2020. Interactions between nitrogen
653 nutrition, canopy architecture and photosynthesis in rice, assessed using high resolution
654 3D reconstruction. *in silico Plants*: diaa017.

655 **Burgess AJ, Retkute R, Preston SP, Jensen OE, Pound MP, Pridmore TP, Murchie**
656 **EH.** 2016. The 4-Dimensional Plant: Effects of Wind-Induced Canopy Movement on
657 Light Fluctuations and Photosynthesis. *Frontiers in Plant Science* **7**: 1392.

658 **Cabrera-Bosquet L, Fournier C, Bricet N, Welcker C, Suard B, Tardieu F.** 2016.
659 High-throughput estimation of incident light, light interception and radiation-use
660 efficiency of thousands of plants in a phenotyping platform. *New Phytologist* **212**: 269-
661 281.

662 **Cao J, Tagliasacchi A, Olson M, Zhang H, Su Z.** 2010. Point cloud skeletons via
663 laplacian based contraction. *2010 Shape Modeling International Conference.* Aix-en-
664 Provence, France: IEEE, 187-197.

665 **Chang TG, Zhao H, Wang N, Song QF, Xiao Y, Qu M, Zhu XG.** 2019. A three-

666 dimensional canopy photosynthesis model in rice with a complete description of the
667 canopy architecture, leaf physiology, and mechanical properties. *Journal of*
668 *Experimental Botany* **70**: 2479-2490.

669 **Chenu K, Van Oosterom EJ, McLean G, Deifel KS, Fletcher A, Geetika G, Tirfessa**
670 **A, Mace ES, Jordan DR, Sulman R, et al.** 2018. Integrating modelling and
671 phenotyping approaches to identify and screen complex traits: transpiration efficiency
672 in cereals. *Journal of Experimental Botany* **69**: 3181-3194.

673 **Cooper M, Gho C, Leafgren R, Tang T, Messina C.** 2014. Breeding drought-tolerant
674 maize hybrids for the US corn-belt: discovery to product. *Journal of Experimental*
675 *Botany* **65**: 6191-6204.

676 **De Pury D, Farquhar G.** 1997. Simple scaling of photosynthesis from leaves to
677 canopies without the errors of big-leaf models. *Plant, Cell and Environment* **20**: 537-
678 557.

679 **Dijkstra EW.** 1959. A note on two problems in connexion with graphs. *Numerische*
680 *mathematik* **1**: 269-271.

681 **Dornbusch T, Watt J, Baccar R, Fournier C, Andrieu B.** 2011. A comparative
682 analysis of leaf shape of wheat, barley and maize using an empirical shape model.
683 *Annals of Botany* **107**: 865-873.

684 **Duan T, Chapman SC, Holland E, Rebetzke GJ, Guo Y, Zheng B.** 2016. Dynamic
685 quantification of canopy structure to characterize early plant vigour in wheat genotypes.
686 *Journal of Experimental Botany* **67**: 4523-4534.

687 **Duncan W, Loomis R, Williams W, Hanau R.** 1967. A model for simulating
688 photosynthesis in plant communities. *Hilgardia* **38**: 181-205.

689 **Duvick DN.** 2005. The Contribution of Breeding to Yield Advances in maize (*Zea mays*
690 L.). *Advances in Agronomy* **86**: 83-145.

691 **Earl HJ, Tollenaar M.** 1997. Maize Leaf Absorptance of Photosynthetically Active
692 Radiation and Its Estimation Using a Chlorophyll Meter. *Crop Science* **37**: 436-440.

693 **Elnashef B, Filin S, Lati RN.** 2019. Tensor-based classification and segmentation of
694 three-dimensional point clouds for organ-level plant phenotyping and growth analysis.

695 *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* **156**: 51-61.

696 **España MaL, Baret F, Aries F, Chelle M, Andrieu B, Prévot L.** 1999. Modeling
697 maize canopy 3D architecture. *Ecological Modelling* **122**: 25-43.

698 **Fischer RA, Edmeades GO.** 2010. Breeding and Cereal Yield Progress. *Crop Science*
699 **50**: S85-S98.

700 **Foo CC, Burgess AJ, Retkute R, Tree-Intong P, Ruban AV, Murchie EH, Lawson**
701 **T.** 2020. Photoprotective energy dissipation is greater in the lower, not the upper,
702 regions of a rice canopy: a 3D analysis. *Journal of Experimental Botany* **71**: 7382-7392.

703 **Furbank RT, Jimenez-Berni JA, George-Jaeggli B, Potgieter AB, Deery DM.** 2019.
704 Field crop phenomics: enabling breeding for radiation use efficiency and biomass in
705 cereal crops. *New Phytologist* **223**: 1714-1727.

706 **Hammer GL, Dong Z, McLean G, Doherty A, Messina C, Schussler J, Zinselmeier**
707 **C, Paszkiewicz S, Cooper M.** 2009. Can Changes in Canopy and/or Root System
708 Architecture Explain Historical Maize Yield Trends in the U.S. Corn Belt? *Crop*
709 *Science* **49**: 299-312.

710 **Han X-F, Jin JS, Wang M-J, Jiang W, Gao L, Xiao L.** 2017. A review of algorithms
711 for filtering the 3D point cloud. *Signal Processing: Image Communication* **57**: 103-112.

712 **Hickey LT, Hafeez NA, Robinson H, Jackson SA, Leal-Bertioli SCM, Tester M,**
713 **Gao C, Godwin ID, Hayes BJ, Wulff BBH.** 2019. Breeding crops to feed 10 billion.
714 *Nature Biotechnology* **37**: 744-754.

715 **Hou T, Zheng B, Xu Z, Yang Y, Chen Y, Guo Y.** 2016. Simplification of leaf surfaces
716 from scanned data: Effects of two algorithms on leaf morphology. *Computers and*
717 *Electronics in Agriculture* **121**: 393-403.

718 **Hui F, Zhu J, Hu P, Meng L, Zhu B, Guo Y, Li B, Ma Y.** 2018. Image-based dynamic
719 quantification and high-accuracy 3D evaluation of canopy structure of plant
720 populations. *Annals of Botany* **121**: 1079-1088.

721 **Jiang Y, Li C, Paterson AH.** 2016. High throughput phenotyping of cotton plant height
722 using depth images under field conditions. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*
723 **130**: 57-68.

724 **Jin S, Su Y, Gao S, Wu F, Hu T, Liu J, Li W, Wang D, Chen S, Jiang Y, et al.** 2018.
725 Deep Learning: Individual Maize Segmentation From Terrestrial Lidar Data Using
726 Faster R-CNN and Regional Growth Algorithms. *Frontiers in Plant Science* **9**: 866.

727 **Jin S, Su Y, Wu F, Pang S, Gao S, Hu T, Liu J, Guo Q.** 2019. Stem–Leaf
728 Segmentation and Phenotypic Trait Extraction of Individual Maize Using Terrestrial
729 LiDAR Data. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* **57**: 1336-1346.

730 **Jin S, Sun X, Wu F, Su Y, Li Y, Song S, Xu K, Ma Q, Baret F, Jiang D, et al.** 2021.
731 Lidar sheds new light on plant phenomics for plant breeding and management: Recent
732 advances and future prospects. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*
733 **171**: 202-223.

734 **Jin X, Zarco-Tejada P, Schmidhalter U, Reynolds MP, Hawkesford MJ, Varshney**
735 **RK, Yang T, Nie C, Li Z, Ming B, et al.** 2021. High-throughput estimation of crop
736 traits: A review of ground and aerial phenotyping platforms. *IEEE Geoscience and*
737 *Remote Sensing Magazine* **9**: 200-231.

738 **Keller B, Matsubara S, Rascher U, Pieruschka R, Steier A, Kraska T, Muller O.**
739 2019. Genotype Specific Photosynthesis x Environment Interactions Captured by
740 Automated Fluorescence Canopy Scans Over Two Fluctuating Growing Seasons.
741 *Frontiers in Plant Science* **10**: 1482.

742 **Ku LX, Zhao WM, Zhang J, Wu LC, Wang CL, Wang PA, Zhang WQ, Chen YH.**
743 2010. Quantitative trait loci mapping of leaf angle and leaf orientation value in maize
744 (*Zea mays* L.). *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* **121**: 951-959.

745 **Lauer S, Hall BD, Mulaosmanovic E, Anderson SR, Nelson B, Smith S.** 2012.
746 Morphological changes in parental lines of pioneer brand maize hybrids in the US
747 central corn belt. *Crop Science* **52**: 1033-1043.

748 **Lee EA, Tollenaar M.** 2007. Physiological Basis of Successful Breeding Strategies for
749 Maize Grain Yield. *Crop Science* **47**: S202-S215.

750 **Lei L, Qiu C, Li Z, Han D, Han L, Zhu Y, Wu J, Xu B, Feng H, Yang H, et al.** 2019.
751 Effect of leaf occlusion on leaf area index inversion of maize using UAV–LiDAR data.
752 *Remote Sensing* **11**: 1067.

753 **Lemon E, Stewart D, Shawcroft R.** 1971. The sun's work in a cornfield. *Science* **174**:
754 371-378.

755 **Liu F, Hu P, Zheng B, Tao D, Zhu B, Guo Y.** 2021. A field-based high-throughput
756 method for acquiring canopy architecture using unmanned aerial vehicle images.
757 *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* **296**: 108231.

758 **Long SP, Zhu X-G, Naidu SL, Ort DR.** 2006. Can improvement in photosynthesis
759 increase crop yields? *Plant, Cell and Environment* **29**: 315-330.

760 **Ma DL, Xie RZ, Niu XK, Li SK, Long HL, Liu YE.** 2014. Changes in the
761 morphological traits of maize genotypes in China between the 1950s and 2000s.
762 *European Journal of Agronomy* **58**: 1-10.

763 **Ma X, Zhu K, Guan H, Feng J, Yu S, Liu G.** 2019. High-Throughput Phenotyping
764 Analysis of Potted Soybean Plants Using Colorized Depth Images Based on A Proximal
765 Platform. *Remote Sensing* **11**: 1085.

766 **Mantilla-Perez MB, Salas Fernandez MG.** 2017. Differential manipulation of leaf
767 angle throughout the canopy: current status and prospects. *Journal of Experimental*
768 *Botany* **68**: 5699-5717.

769 **McCormick RF, Truong SK, Mullet JE.** 2016. 3D sorghum reconstructions from
770 depth images identify QTL regulating shoot architecture. *Plant Physiology* **172**: 823-
771 834.

772 **Meacham-Hensold K, Fu P, Wu J, Serbin S, Montes CM, Ainsworth E, Guan K,**
773 **Dracup E, Pederson T, Driever S, et al.** 2020. Plot-level rapid screening for
774 photosynthetic parameters using proximal hyperspectral imaging. *Journal of*
775 *Experimental Botany* **71**: 2312-2328.

776 **Mock J, Pearce R.** 1975. An ideotype of maize. *Euphytica* **24**: 613-623.

777 **Myers SS, Smith MR, Guth S, Golden CD, Vaitla B, Mueller ND, Dangour AD,**
778 **Huybers P.** 2017. Climate Change and Global Food Systems: Potential Impacts on
779 Food Security and Undernutrition. *Annual Review of Public Health* **38**: 259-277.

780 **Ort DR, Merchant SS, Alric J, Barkan A, Blankenship RE, Bock R, Croce R,**
781 **Hanson MR, Hibberd JM, Long SP, et al.** 2015. Redesigning photosynthesis to

782 sustainably meet global food and bioenergy demand. *Proceedings of the National*
783 *Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **112**: 8529-8536.

784 **Pendleton J, Smith G, Winter S, Johnston T.** 1968. Field investigations of the
785 relationships of leaf angle in corn (*zea mays* l.) to grain yield and apparent
786 photosynthesis 1. *Agronomy Journal* **60**: 422-424.

787 **Peng S, Khush G, Cassman K.** 1994. Evolution of the new plant ideotype for
788 increased yield potential. In: Cassman KG, ed. *Breaking the Yield Barrier: Proceedings*
789 *of a Workshop on Rice Yield Potential in Favorable Environments*. Los Banos,
790 Philippines: International Rice Research Institute, 5-20.

791 **Peng S, Khush GS, Virk P, Tang Q, Zou Y.** 2008. Progress in ideotype breeding to
792 increase rice yield potential. *Field Crops Research* **108**: 32-38.

793 **Perez RP, Fournier C, Cabrera-Bosquet L, Artzet S, Pradal C, Bricet N, Chen**
794 **TW, Chapuis R, Welcker C, Tardieu F.** 2019. Changes in the vertical distribution of
795 leaf area enhanced light interception efficiency in maize over generations of selection.
796 *Plant, Cell and Environment* **42**: 2105–2119.

797 **Perez RPA, Costes E, Théveny F, Griffon S, Caliman J-P, Dausat J.** 2018. 3D plant
798 model assessed by terrestrial LiDAR and hemispherical photographs: A useful tool for
799 comparing light interception among oil palm progenies. *Agricultural and Forest*
800 *Meteorology* **249**: 250-263.

801 **Pound MP, French AP, Murchie EH, Pridmore TP.** 2014. Automated recovery of
802 three-dimensional models of plant shoots from multiple color images. *Plant Physiology*
803 **166**: 1688-1698.

804 **Rabbani T, Van Den Heuvel F, Vosselmann G.** 2006. Segmentation of point clouds
805 using smoothness constraint. *International archives of photogrammetry, remote sensing*
806 *and spatial information sciences* **36**: 248-253.

807 **Ray DK, Ramankutty N, Mueller ND, West PC, Foley JA.** 2012. Recent patterns of
808 crop yield growth and stagnation. *Nature Communications* **3**: 1293.

809 **Salas Fernandez MG, Bao Y, Tang L, Schnable PS.** 2017. A High-Throughput, Field-
810 Based Phenotyping Technology for Tall Biomass Crops. *Plant Physiology* **174**: 2008-

811 2022.

812 **Sellers P, Randall D, Collatz G, Berry J, Field C, Dazlich D, Zhang C, Collelo G,**
813 **Bounoua L.** 1996. A revised land surface parameterization (SiB2) for atmospheric
814 GCMs. Part I: Model formulation. *Journal of Climate* **9**: 676-705.

815 **Silva-Perez V, Molero G, Serbin SP, Condon AG, Reynolds MP, Furbank RT,**
816 **Evans JR.** 2018. Hyperspectral reflectance as a tool to measure biochemical and
817 physiological traits in wheat. *Journal of Experimental Botany* **69**: 483-496.

818 **Sinoquet H, Moulia B, Bonhomme R.** 1991. Estimating the three-dimensional
819 geometry of a maize crop as an input of radiation models: comparison between three-
820 dimensional digitizing and plant profiles. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* **55**: 233-
821 249.

822 **Song Q, Srinivasan V, Long SP, Zhu XG.** 2020. Decomposition analysis on soybean
823 productivity increase under elevated CO₂ using 3-D canopy model reveals synergistic
824 effects of CO₂ and light in photosynthesis. *Annals of Botany* **126**: 601-614.

825 **Song Q, Wang Y, Qu M, Ort DR, Zhu XG.** 2017. The impact of modifying
826 photosystem antenna size on canopy photosynthetic efficiency-Development of a new
827 canopy photosynthesis model scaling from metabolism to canopy level processes. *Plant,*
828 *Cell and Environment* **40**: 2946-2957.

829 **Song Q, Zhang G, Zhu X-G.** 2013. Optimal crop canopy architecture to maximise
830 canopy photosynthetic CO₂ uptake under elevated CO₂ – a theoretical study using a
831 mechanistic model of canopy photosynthesis. *Functional Plant Biology* **40**: 109-124.

832 **Srinivasan V, Kumar P, Long SP.** 2017. Decreasing, not increasing, leaf area will
833 raise crop yields under global atmospheric change. *Global Change Biology* **23**: 1626-
834 1635.

835 **Su W, Zhu D, Huang J, Guo H.** 2018. Estimation of the vertical leaf area profile of
836 corn (*Zea mays*) plants using terrestrial laser scanning (TLS). *Computers and*
837 *Electronics in Agriculture* **150**: 5-13.

838 **Sun S, Li C, Paterson AH, Jiang Y, Xu R, Robertson JS, Snider JL, Chee PW.** 2018.
839 In-field high throughput phenotyping and cotton plant growth analysis using LiDAR.

840 *Frontiers in Plant Science* **9**: 16.

841 **Thapa S, Zhu F, Walia H, Yu H, Ge Y.** 2018. A Novel LiDAR-Based Instrument for
842 High-Throughput, 3D Measurement of Morphological Traits in Maize and Sorghum.
843 *Sensors (Basel)* **18**: 1187.

844 **Thornley JH.** 2002. Instantaneous canopy photosynthesis: analytical expressions for
845 sun and shade leaves based on exponential light decay down the canopy and an
846 acclimated non-rectangular hyperbola for leaf photosynthesis. *Annals of Botany* **89**:
847 451-458.

848 **Tian F, Bradbury PJ, Brown PJ, Hung H, Sun Q, Flint-Garcia S, Rocheford TR,**
849 **McMullen MD, Holland JB, Buckler ES.** 2011. Genome-wide association study of
850 leaf architecture in the maize nested association mapping population. *Nature Genetics*
851 **43**: 159-162.

852 **Torr PHS, Zisserman A.** 2000. MLESAC: A New Robust Estimator with Application
853 to Estimating Image Geometry. *Computer Vision and Image Understanding* **78**: 138-
854 156.

855 **Townsend AJ, Retkute R, Chinnathambi K, Randall JWP, Foulkes J, Carmo-Silva**
856 **E, Murchie EH.** 2018. Suboptimal Acclimation of Photosynthesis to Light in Wheat
857 Canopies. *Plant Physiology* **176**: 1233-1246.

858 **Virlet N, Sabermanesh K, Sadeghi-Tehran P, Hawkesford MJ.** 2017. Field
859 Scanalyzer: An automated robotic field phenotyping platform for detailed crop
860 monitoring. *Functional Plant Biology* **44**: 143-153.

861 **Wahabzada M, Paulus S, Kersting K, Mahlein A-K.** 2015. Automated interpretation
862 of 3D laserscanned point clouds for plant organ segmentation. *BMC Bioinformatics* **16**:
863 248.

864 **Wang X, Guo Y, Li B, Wang X, Ma Y.** 2006. Evaluating a three dimensional model
865 of diffuse photosynthetically active radiation in maize canopies. *International Journal*
866 *of Biometeorology* **50**: 349-357.

867 **Wang Y, Song Q, Jaiswal D, P. de Souza A, Long SP, Zhu X-G.** 2017. Development
868 of a Three-Dimensional Ray-Tracing Model of Sugarcane Canopy Photosynthesis and

869 Its Application in Assessing Impacts of Varied Row Spacing. *BioEnergy Research* **10**:
870 626-634.

871 **Wang Y, Wen W, Wu S, Wang C, Yu Z, Guo X, Zhao C.** 2018. Maize Plant
872 Phenotyping: Comparing 3D Laser Scanning, Multi-View Stereo Reconstruction, and
873 3D Digitizing Estimates. *Remote Sensing* **11**: 63.

874 **Wen W, Guo X, Li B, Wang C, Wang Y, Yu Z, Wu S, Fan J, Gu S, Lu X.** 2019.
875 Estimating canopy gap fraction and diffuse light interception in 3D maize canopy using
876 hierarchical hemispheres. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* **276-277**: 107594.

877 **Wu S, Wen W, Xiao B, Guo X, Du J, Wang C, Wang Y.** 2019. An Accurate Skeleton
878 Extraction Approach From 3D Point Clouds of Maize Plants. *Frontiers in Plant Science*
879 **10**: 248.

880 **Xu W, Liu C, Wang K, Xie R, Ming B, Wang Y, Zhang G, Liu G, Zhao R, Fan P,**
881 **et al.** 2017. Adjusting maize plant density to different climatic conditions across a large
882 longitudinal distance in China. *Field Crops Research* **212**: 126-134.

883 **Yang L, Zhai R, Shi P, Wu P.** 2016. Segmentation of crop organs through region
884 growing in 3D space. *2016 Fifth International Conference on Agro-Geoinformatics*
885 *(Agro-Geoinformatics)*. Tianjin, China: IEEE, 1-6.

886 **Zhang X, Huang C, Wu D, Qiao F, Li W, Duan L, Wang K, Xiao Y, Chen G, Liu**
887 **Q, et al.** 2017. High-throughput phenotyping and QTL mapping reveals the genetic
888 architecture of maize plant growth. *Plant Physiology* **173**: 1554-1564.

889 **Zheng B, Shi L, Ma Y, Deng Q, Li B, Guo Y.** 2008. Comparison of architecture among
890 different cultivars of hybrid rice using a spatial light model based on 3-D digitising.
891 *Functional Plant Biology* **35**: 900-910.

892 **Zheng BY, Ma YT, Li BG, Yan G, Deng QY.** 2011. Assessment of the influence of
893 global dimming on the photosynthetic production of rice based on three-dimensional
894 modeling. *Science China Earth Sciences* **54**: 290-297.

895 **Zhu B, Liu F, Xie Z, Guo Y, Li B, Ma Y.** 2020. Quantification of light interception
896 within image-based 3-D reconstruction of sole and intercropped canopies over the
897 entire growth season. *Annals of Botany* **126**: 701-712.

898 **Zhu C, Miao T, Xu T, Yang T, Li N.** 2020. Stem-leaf segmentation and phenotypic
899 trait extraction of maize shoots from three-dimensional point cloud. *arXiv*. doi:
900 *arXiv:2009.03108*.

901 **Zhu XG, Long SP, Ort DR.** 2010. Improving photosynthetic efficiency for greater
902 yield. *Annual Review of Plant Biology* **61**: 235-261.

903

904

905

906

907

908

909

910

911
 912
 913
 914
 915
 916

Fig. 1 A pipeline of extracting the target *Zea mays* plant from the original point clouds. We used point clouds for W64A at 44 DAS. The original point clouds (a) were firstly proceeded to remove the soil surface to generate the second point clouds (b), and then we extracted the target plant (c) by denoising outliers.

917
 918
 919
 920
 921

Fig. 2 A pipeline of *Zea mays* plant organ segmentation. The plant point clouds of A619 at 37 DAS were transferred to a skeleton by a Laplacian based method (a) and clusters based on the region growing method (d). Leaf skeletons (b) were extracted from the plant skeleton. Reference leaf point clouds (c) were obtained from the plant point clouds

922 according to the leaf skeletons. According to reference leaf point clouds and angles
 923 between clusters and stem direction, small clusters (d) were classified to organ point
 924 clouds (e) and unclassified point clouds. The unclassified point clouds were classified
 925 into clusters by the region growing method (f). The larger clusters from unclassified
 926 point clouds were merged into organ point clouds (g) according to the similarity of
 927 normal and curvature of points between the larger cluster and neighbouring organ point
 928 clouds. Finally, the remaining clusters were merged into organ point clouds by a
 929 Euclidean distance-based method (h).
 930

931
 932 Fig. 3 An example of *Zea mays* leaf architectural trait extraction. Leaf length (a, red
 933 line) is the distance of the shortest path between the leaf base and the leaf tip. Leaf
 934 width (a, yellow line) is the distance of the shortest path between points between leaf
 935 edges. The smooth leaf edge (a, blue line), which is defined as the leaf edge with the
 936 distortion and undulation removed, was used to evaluate the leaf flatness and leaf
 937 smoothness. The sub-figure is a special case during the extraction of the leaf tip, purple
 938 and grey lines indicate points belonging to Part 1(a, purple line) and Part 2(a, grey line),
 939 respectively. Leaf area was calculated by the meshed point clouds (b) (see the Materials
 940 and Methods section for details).

941

942

943 Fig. 4 An example of the new ideotype design method. The example is based on point
 944 clouds of *Zea mays* plants. The leaf length (a) and the leaf width (b) of original point
 945 clouds (red point clouds) were increased by 20% (blue point clouds). The leaf angle (c)
 946 of original point clouds was reduced by 20 degrees. The changed leaf point clouds of
 947 B73 at 58 DAS were assembled into the changed plant point clouds with 20% less upper
 948 leaf angle (d). The surface reconstruction was conducted to generate meshed plants
 949 consisting of a set of triangles (e). Based on the meshed plants, the virtual canopy with
 950 10 plants/m² (f) was obtained. The central canopy (f, space within the blue voxel,) was
 951 used to evaluate canopy photosynthesis. The horizontal size of the central canopy is 4
 952 × plant distance × row distance (see the Materials and Methods section for details).

953

954

955 Fig. 5 The canopy occupation volume in normal view (a), front view (b) and top view
 956 (c) of a *Zea mays* plant. The space of the meshed plant was divided into a set of small
 957 3D voxels (blue voxels). If a voxel contains triangles of meshed plant, the voxel is
 958 regarded as the occupied voxel (yellow voxels). The sum of occupied voxel volume is
 959 the canopy occupation volume. The size of voxels is 20 cm×20 cm×20cm in this main
 960 figure and is 1 cm×1 cm×1cm in calculation (a, sub-fig).

961

962

963 Fig. 6 The result of organ segmentation in three cultivars of *Zea mays* plants at four
 964 growth stages. The different organs were represented by a different colour.

965

967

968 Fig.7 Comparison of leaf lengths(a), maximal leaf width(b) and leaf area(c) between

969 manual measurement and estimation from reconstructed *Zea mays* plants using LiDAR.

970

971

972 Fig. 8 The leaf architectural traits in the upper and lower parts for three cultivars of *Zea*

973 *mays* plants at four different DASs. The distribution of trait values for different leaf

974 architectural traits is described by the box plots, where the box length provides the

975 interquartile range (IQR), the bottom of the box is the 25th percentile (first quartile, q_1),

976 the top of the box is the 75th percentile (third quartile, q_3) and the horizontal line within

977 the box is the median value. The lower whisker corresponds to $q_1-1.5IQR$, or to the

978 minimum estimate, and the upper whisker corresponds to $q_3+1.5IQR$, or to the

979 maximum estimate. The dots denote values outside the whisker limits. The error bars
 980 indicate the standard deviation. Different small letters in each group indicate significant
 981 differences at $P < 0.05$.

982

983

984 Fig. 9 The comparisons of the daily canopy photosynthetic CO_2 uptake rate per unit
 985 ground (A_c ; a), canopy occupation volume per unit ground area (COV ; b), leaf area
 986 index (c), daily light interception per unit ground (LI ; d), facet angle (e) and canopy
 987 coverage (f) in canopies with different canopy architectures produced by changing
 988 upper leaf angle of *Zea mays* plants (A619) at 58 DAS in 10 plants/ m^2 (g). The
 989 percentage changes of the leaf angle depend on the original leaf angle. When leaf

990 angles of 80% individual leaves become 0 degrees, we defined the current percentage
 991 change as the lowest percentage change. The highest percentage change was obtained
 992 similarly. When leaf angles of 80% individual leaves are equal to 90 degrees, we
 993 defined the current percentage change as the highest percentage change. Five
 994 percentage changes were set between the lowest and highest percentage changes with
 995 an equal interval corresponding to the virtual canopies 1-5 (g) (see the Materials and
 996 Methods section for details). Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

997

Density (plant m⁻²) • 12 ▲ 10 ■ 8 Cultivars • A619 • B73 • W64A

998

999 Fig. 10 The relationship between leaf area index (LAI), canopy occupation volume per
 1000 unit ground area (COV), facet angle (FA), canopy coverage (CC) and daily canopy
 1001 photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate per unit ground area of *Zea mays* plants. The canopy
 1002 architectures of three cultivars were changed by altering parameters in the upper and
 1003 lower parts. Either leaf area or leaf angle was modified. See Fig. 4 for detailed methods
 1004 of changing leaf area, leaf angle.

1005

1006

1007 Fig. 11 The relationship between canopy occupation volume and canopy photosynthesis
 1008 of *Zea mays* plants. a) the change of canopy occupation volume between leaves that
 1009 were spread out (a; case 1) and overlapped leaves (a; case 2). b) the difference of light
 1010 interception between overlapped leaves and leaves spread out. c) the change of canopy
 1011 occupation volume among big leaf angles (c; angle 1), intermediate leaf angles (c; angle
 1012 2) and small leaf angles (c; angle 3). d) the difference of daily canopy photosynthetic
 1013 CO₂ uptake rate per unit leaf area among three different upper leaf angles of W64A at
 1014 58 DAS.

1015

1016 Methods. S1 The new method to segment of plant organs

1017 Methods. S2 The method of changing plant architecture

1018

1019 Fig. S1 Light response curves of three cultivars of *Zea mays* plants at 58 DAS.

1020 Fig. S2 Comparisons of the daily light interception per unit ground (Light
 1021 interception), the daily canopy photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate per unit ground (A_c)
 1022 and the light use efficiency (LUE) for *Zea mays* canopies with different canopy
 1023 architectures changed from three cultivars simulated under three planting densities
 1024 using the A-Q curve of A619.

1025 Fig. S3 Changes of the parameters describing *Zea mays* canopy architectures when

1026 leaf length, width and leaf angles are altered under three different planting densities.
1027 Fig. S4 The relationship between leaf area index (LAI), canopy occupation volume per
1028 unit ground area (COV), facet angle (FA), canopy coverage (CC) and daily canopy
1029 photosynthetic CO₂ uptake rate per unit ground area of *Zea mays* plants.
1030
1031 Table. S1 The ambient environmental data
1032 Table. S2 The measured SPAD, leaf transmittance and reflectance for 3 cultivars of *Zea*
1033 *mays* plants at 58 DAS.
1034 Table. S3 The accuracy of organ segmentation for three cultivars of *Zea mays* plants at
1035 four growth stages
1036
1037 Notes S1. Supporting equations
1038
1039